

Effect of Different Liquid Media and Cultural Condition on Biomass Production of *Sclerotium Rolfsii*

Vishwajit R. Mhaske¹, Anil D. Adsare², Sudarshan R. Mane³ and Madhukar S. Wadikar⁴

¹Department of Botany Shikshan Maharshi Dnyandeo Mohekar Mahavidyalaya, Kallam, Dist-Dharashiv.

²Department of Botany, Arts, Commerce and Science College, Maregaon, Dist-Yavatmal.

³Department of Botany, Shri Swami Samarth Arts and Science Senior College Ruibhar, Dist-Dharashiv.

⁴Department of Botany, R. B. Attal Arts, Science and Commerce College, Georai, Dist- Beed.

Corresponding Author – Vishwajit R. Mhaske

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.19755489

Abstract:

In the present investigation effect of different liquid media and different physical parameters like pH and temperature to standardized proper cultural condition for maximum biomass production of *Sclerotium rolfsii* was carried out. The results revealed that among the media tested Glucose Peptone broth significantly induced the biomass production as compare to other media after 10 days of incubation. The range of pH 6 and 25^oC temperature was optimum for biomass production of *Sclerotium rolfsii* after 10 days of incubation.

Introduction:

Sclerotium rolfsii is a necrotrophic soilborne plant pathogen forming sclerotia as a survival structure distributed worldwide. *Sclerotium rolfsii* is polyphagous, ubiquitous, facultative and most destructive soil borne fungus. It is an anamorph of *Athelia rolfsii*. Pier Andrea Saccardo, initially identified the species in 1911, based on specimens brought to him by Peter Henry Rolfs, who believed the unnamed fungus was the cause of tomato blight in Florida. He named the species *Sclerotium rolfsii* and placed it in the old *Sclerotium* genus. Because of prolific growth of *Sclerotium rolfsii* and ability to produce persistent sclerotia, it is contributing in high degree of economic losses (Mahen et al., 1995)⁽⁶⁾. The pathogen has a significant economic impact on a variety of crops. The host range of *Sclerotium rolfsii* is very broad, encompassing several horticultural and agronomical crops all over the world (Aycock,1996)⁽¹⁾. The fungus

attacks over 500 species of plants from over 100 families.

Fungi have morphogenic and cultural variations, hence a comprehensive study of the effects of media, temperature and pH on biomass production of *Sclerotium rolfsii* was carried out.

Materials and Method:

Collection and Isolation of Fungi:

Soil samples were collected from different localities of Marathwada region. The soil samples were collected by digging 10 to 15 cm depth using sterile spatulas and five soil samples were randomly collected approximately 100gm from each sampling site in pre sterilized zip-lock bags. Isolation of fungi were done by dilution plate method (Waksman, 1916), one gram of each soil sample was taken and added in test tube containing 10ml of sterile distilled water. The suspension was serially diluted five times 10⁻¹ to 10⁻⁵ in sterile distilled water. The Suspension obtained after vigorous mixing of the

soil samples were allowed to stand for 20 min. 0.5ml of each aqueous dilutions of soil suspensions were inoculated on Petri plates amended with Potato dextrose agar. Trace amount of Streptomycin was added in PDA media to avoid bacterial contamination. Spread plate and Pour plate techniques were used. The inoculated plates were incubated at 30°C for 7 days. Different fungal colonies were observed and sub cultured to obtain pure cultures.

Identification of Fungi:

Identification of fungi were done on the basis of morphological and microscopic observations like colony colour, margin of the colony, growth pattern, sporulation and pigment production. The identification and further confirmation fungi was made by preparing slides of the fungal growth and observing them under compound microscope and slide culture technique. The identification was made with the help of manuals, The Illustration of fungi by Mukadam *et al.*, (2005)⁽⁷⁾ A manual of soil fungi by Gilman (2001)⁽³⁾, A hand book of soil fungi by Nagmani and Kunwar (2005)⁽⁸⁾.

Effect of different liquid media on biomass production of Fungi:

The study of different cultural media for Biomass production of fungi investigated by 6 different liquid media like Potato Dextrose broth, Malt Extract broth, Glucose Peptone broth, Czapek Dox broth, Glucose Nitrate broth, Yeast Extract Peptone Dextrose broth. 50ml of each broth were dispensed into 250 ml Erlenmeyer flasks and autoclaved at 121°C (15psi) for 20 minutes. Each flask was inoculated with 5mm mycelial disc taken from actively growing of 7 days old *Sclerotium rolfsii* culture. After 8 days incubation period each flask was filter through Whatman No. 1 filter paper. The mycelium dried

at 70⁰ C in an oven. All experiment were conducted in triplicate. The dry weight was calculated by using the following formula:

Dry Weight = (weight of filter paper + mycelium) - (weight of blank filter paper).

Effects of temperature on biomass production of Fungi

The effect of temperature on biomass production of fungi was investigated by using the malt extract broth medium incubating at various range of temperature (25⁰C -50⁰C). After the incubation period the culture of each conical flask were filter through Whatman No 1 filter paper, the filter paper with mycelium were dried in oven at 70⁰ C. The dry weight was calculated as mention above.

Effect of pH on biomass production of fungi:

The effect of pH on biomass production of tested fungi was investigated by using the malt extract broth medium prepared with various pH ranging from pH 4 to pH 8. The pH of the medium was adjusted from pH 4 to pH 8 with 0.1 NaOH and 0.1 N HCl with the pH meter. After the incubation period the culture of each conical flask were filter through Whatman No. 1 filter paper, filter paper with mycelium were dried in oven at 70⁰ C. The dry weight was calculated as mention above.

Result and Discussion:

In the present study about 50 different fungal colonies were observed. The identification of *Sclerotium rolfsii* was carried out on the basis of morphological and colony characters and by slide culture technique.

Effect of different media on biomass production of *Sclerotium rolfsii*:

In order to study effect of different media on biomass production six different media were

used like PDB, CZB, MB, GNB, GPB and YPB. Maximum biomass production was observed on Glucose Peptone broth (420). Whereas minimum biomass production was observed on Czapek Dox broth (140). While Yeast Extract Peptone Dextrose broth showed (330) followed by Potato Dextrose broth (300). Glucose Nitrate broth and Malt Extract broth observed dry weight (290 and 150) respectively (Table no.1 and Graph no. 1). Kushwaha et al., (2019)⁽⁵⁾ examined total of seven liquid media were used for studying the growth of *Sclerotium rolfsii* in Lentil. Their results reported that potato-dextrose medium was most suitable for mycelial growth. Ravikumar G Vaniya et al (2022)⁽⁹⁾ examined total of seven liquid media for studying the growth of *Sclerotium rolfsii*. They reported that Dry mycelial weight observed significantly superior on Potato Dextrose broth medium. Sahana N. et al., (2017)⁽¹¹⁾ also reported the maximum dry mycelial weight of fungus in potato dextrose broth.

Table No. 1 Effect of different media on biomass production of *Sclerotium rolfsii*

Sr. No.	Different Media	Dry Weight (mg)
1	PDB	300
2	CZB	140
3	MB	150
4	GNB	290
5	GPB	420
6	YPB	330

Dry weight of biomass expressed in mg.

Effect of different temperature on biomass production of *Sclerotium rolfsii*:

Effect of temperature on biomass production of *Sclerotium rolfsii* was observed by maintaining the different temperature levels for incubation. Maximum biomass production was found at 25⁰C temperature. While at temperature 30⁰C and 35⁰C dry weight was observed (190) respectively. None of biomass observed at 45⁰C and 50⁰ C temperature (Table no. 2 and Graph no. 2). Similar result was reported by earlier coworkers Ayed F. et al (2018)⁽²⁾, Tripathi B. P. and Khare N. (2006)⁽¹²⁾. Above 40⁰ C temperature growth of the fungus was reduced. These finding are similar with Hussain A. et al (2006)⁽⁴⁾ They observed that the growth of *Sclerotium rolfsii* decreased significantly above 35⁰C temperature.

Table no. 2 Effect of different temperature on biomass production of *Sclerotium rolfsii*

Sr. No.	Temperature	Dry Weight (mg)
1	25	220
2	30	190
3	35	190
4	40	160
5	45	000
6	50	000

Dry weight of biomass expressed in mg.

Effect of different pH on biomass production of *Sclerotium rolfsii*:

The study of effect of different pH ranges on biomass production of *Sclerotium rolfsii* carried out by maintaining the different pH levels of medium i.e. 4 to 8 pH. The maximum biomass production was observed on pH 6 (230). The range of pH 4.5 (220) and 6 (230) to 6.5 (220) is optimum pH range for biomass production. At acidic pH i.e. 4 (80) and at basic pH i.e. 8 (100) biomass production was significantly reduced. The remaining pH showed mycelial dry weight on pH 5 (160), pH 5.5 (210), pH 7 (190) and pH 7.5 (120) respectively (Table no. 3 and Graph no. 3). Raut M. K. et al (2015)⁽¹⁰⁾ showed maximum biomass production on pH 6.

Table no. 3 Effect of different pH on biomass production of *Sclerotium rolfsii*

Sr. No.	pH	Dry Weight (mg)
1	4	80
2	4.5	220
3	5	160
4	5.5	210
5	6	230
6	6.5	220
7	7	190
8	7.5	120
9	8	100

Dry weight of biomass expressed in mg.

References:

1. Aycock R. (1966) Stem rot and other diseases caused by *Sclerotium rolfsii*.

North Carolina Agric. Expt. Station., 136-202.

2. Ayed F., Jabnoun Khiareddine H., Aydi Ben Abdallah R., Daami Remadi M. (2018) Effect of Temperatures and Culture Media on *Sclerotium rolfsii* Mycelial Growth, Sclerotial Formation and Germination. Journal of Plant Pathology & Microbiology.; 9(8):446.
3. Gilman J. C. A (2001) Manual of soil fungi second Indian edition, Biotech books Delhi,.
4. Hussain A., Muhammad I. S., Ayub N., Haqqani A. M. (2006) Physiological study of *Sclerotium rolfsii* Sacc. Pak J Plant Patho.; 2: 102-106.
5. Kushwaha Shiva Kant, Sanjeev Kumar, Balkishan Chaudhary and Ravit Sahu (2019) Effect of Different Media, pH and Temperature on Growth and Sclerotia Formation of *Sclerotium rolfsii* Sacc. causing Collar rot of Lentil. Chemical Science Review and Letters.; 8(29): 01-05.
6. Mahen, V. K., Mayer, C. D., Brennemen T. B. & McDonald D. (1995) Stem and pod rots of groundnut. Information Bulletin No. 4, ICRISAT; 28.
7. Mukadam D. S., Chavan A. M., Patil M. S. and Patil A. (2005) Illustration of fungi Kailas publication, Aurangabad.
8. Nagmani A, Kunwar I. K. and Manoharachary C. (2005) Hand book of soil fungi. Published by K. International Pvt. Ltd New Delhi.
9. Ravikumar G Vaniya, Pushpendra Singh and A. J. Deshmukh (2022) Effect of different cultural media on growth of different isolates of *Sclerotium rolfsii* Sacc. causing stem rot of Indian bean The Pharma Innovation Journal.; 11(4): 14-19.

10. Rout M. K., Mohanty P., Dash S. R and Parida D. (2015) Studies on Effect of pH, Temperature and Relative Humidity on Growth and Sporulation of *Alternaria alternata* and *Sclerotium rolfsii* Causing Bud Rot and Collar Rot in Marigold. Trends in Biosciences.; 8(24): 6785-6787.
11. Sahana N, Banakar V. B., Sanath Kumar and Thejesha A. G. (2017) Morphological and cultural Studies of *S. rolfsii* Sacc. Causing foot rot disease of tomato. International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences.; 6(3): 1146-1153.
12. Tripathi B. P. and Khare N. (2006) Growth of *Sclerotium rolfsii* of chick pea as induced by bioagents. Ann. Plant. Prot. Sci.; 13: 492-493.